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Using an Interferometric radar to assess post-earthquake damage status of an urban building: a case study

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Abstract. This paper reports the use of an interferometric radar to support the detection of the main vibrating frequencies of a building damaged after the Mw 5.1, May 11th 2011, Lorca earthquake (Southeast Spain). The surveyed building, a reinforced concrete structure, was located in the San Fernando neighbourhood of the city of Lorca, where the earthquake caused severe damages. The radar survey was carried out some months after the earthquake. To assess the building capacity and fragility, a pushover analysis has been carried out. The building has been modelled by using the SAP2000 software. The goal of the study is to detect changes of the main natural frequencies of a specific building after the earthquake and, through a comparison of the building frequencies before and after the earthquake, to estimate the effect of the earthquake on the monitored building.

1. Introduction

The capability of a radar interferometer to detect displacements with sub-millimeter accuracy, main frequencies, and modal shapes of civil structures, is well-consolidated and a wide literature is available about different applications [1]. Although this technique is able to provide only an estimate of a component of the actual displacement, i.e. the radar Line-Of-Sight component, it can consistently contribute to check its structural health conditions providing estimates of their vibrating characteristics and its main vibration modes. In the last decade, literature showed the successful monitoring of different structures and facilities (bridges, buildings, wind towers). In the case of urban building, the small extent of the vibrating amplitude under micro tremor, makes the detection more difficult to tackle [2][3]. Anyway, this technique can be particularly useful when the use of in situ sensors needs hazardous installations, as in the emergency case, e.g. after an earthquake, and when a fast and safe survey is demanded. This paper reports the use of an interferometric radar to support the detection of the main vibrating frequencies of a building damaged after the Mw 5.1, May 11th 2011, Lorca earthquake that caused localized damage in the Region of Murcia, Spain. The surveyed building was located in the San Fernando district neighbourhood of the city of Lorca (Murcia, Spain), where the earthquake caused severe damages in 15 buildings which were finally demolished three years after the earthquake. The radar survey was carried out some months after the earthquake and before final demolition. The building

has a reinforced concrete structure with unidirectional floors, having a thickness of 20 cm, and closed with infill-unreinforced masonry walls. The goal of the study is to detect changes of the main natural frequencies of a specific building after the earthquake. Because the vibrational behaviour of the undamaged building remains unknown, the frequencies of the undamaged building are calculated through a pushover analysis of the building in the pre-event status, while an interferometric radar is used, during the post-event, for the estimate of the vibrating frequencies of the potentially damaged building. To assess the building capacity and fragility, a pushover analysis has been carried out. The building has been modelled by using the SAP2000 software [4].

The fundamental periods measured on the damaged building using the interferometric radar, are in the range of the values obtained by means of the numeric procedures, and computational assessments are consistent with the observed damage. This agreement allows considering radar interferometry a complementary non-invasive prospecting tool to assess the structural health conditions in a post-earthquake scenario, thus contributing to estimate the damage index, and validating the simulation results. This approach could be also used for rapid screening, immediately after the disaster with alerting and supporting purposes. The paper is organized in the following sections. Starting from this introduction, the rationale of the study is introduced. A short description of the structural model used to simulate the response of the undamaged building is also given. The variation of the vibrating period expected from the model for the damaged building is analysed. The experimental results are then commented: radar outputs, combined with the results of the numerical analysis of the modelled structure, are used to estimate the damage condition. Some final observations conclude the paper.

2. The rationale

When a damage occurs to a building, due for example to a seismic event, from a simplified point of view, the stiffness of the structure reduces. Considering the vibrating behaviour of the structure, the main natural periods are expected to increase correspondingly. In fig. 1 we show a simple representation of this rationale: here the structure is represented by an elemental oscillating mass.

Figure 1. Simple scheme to explain the main rationale of the paper from left to right: the mechanical model, k stiffness, m mass, and T oscillating period. The expression of the vibrating period and the effect of an earthquake (the red star).

On this basis, if we are able to compare the period before and after the event, after evaluating with a sensitivity study the relationship between the effect of modifications of the structural elements of the building, and the main periods, we could estimate the damage. Definitely, because an earthquake is not predictable, an experimental measurement of the natural periods of the structures is usually not available, but we can calculate the main vibration modes of a building using a numeric approach. Starting from the geometry and the structural characteristics of the building, we can estimate, with a certain approximation, the behaviour of the structure in presence of an energizing force, as the

acceleration induced by a seismic wave. The model can be also used to estimate the damage occurred to the building. Finally, comparing the periods of the undamaged building and those measured after the earthquake, we can estimate the damage degree. Note that here we consider a damage as changes introduced into the mechanical properties of a building, which affects the behaviour and performance of the building.

3. The event and the structural model results

3.1. The undamaged building

The investigated building is a reinforced concrete building, representative of a group of 15 housing buildings located in the neighborhood of San Fernando in the city of Lorca (Murcia, Spain) (Fig. 2). This building was severely damaged during the Lorca (Spain) May 11th 2011 earthquake [5]. The building, today demolished and substituted by a new construction, had 5 stories and six spans in the studied direction. The design for most buildings was based on a diaphanous first level as a solution in front of severe floods as those occurred in the region during the 1960-70 decade. This soft-storey configuration had influenced the building seismic performance due to the concentration of shear forces and displacements on the weaker frames induced by an abrupt difference on stiffness in height. The common failure mechanism in the damage report of the survey completed after the earthquake is ascribed to this effect. The described damage distribution mainly affected the first level. The few infill walls present in the entrance (first level) of most buildings collapsed, and the typical infill failure was described as induced by the movement of the surrounding frame. Regarding the columns of the first level, plastic hinges appeared at the bottom and top ends of almost all columns. Additionally, a reduced and non-severe distribution of the damage was observed in the upper levels. The undamaged building has been modelled and analyzed by using the SAP2000 software [4]. The obtained periods, listed in Table 1, are within the expected range of periods when similar buildings are considered, i.e. in the range from $T=0.08.n$ to $T=0.13.n$ seconds, where n is the number of levels. Table 1 lists also the mass participation and orientation of the first three modes.

Table 1. Periods obtained through the simulation for the undamaged building.

Mode	Period (s)	% Mass participation	Axis
Mode 1	0.570	84.1	Horizontal Y
Mode 2	0.567	84	Rotational Z
Mode 3	0.454	73	Horizontal X

3.2. The earthquake event and the damaged building modelling

The reinforced concrete building studied in this work was severely damaged during the Lorca (Spain) May 11th 2011 earthquake (Fig. 2b), which with an $M_w=5.1$ magnitude produced an anomalous high acceleration ($PGA=0.37g$) in the city [5].

Figure 2. Shape and size of simulated building. Arrows indicate the elements where the damages have been simulated.

In Table 2 the periods obtained through the simulation for the different worsening damage conditions of the building are reported; only the first mode is considered. The simulated damage degrees consist of three steps: D1, breakage and detachment of walls of first floor; D2 rotation of the feet of pillars; D3 crushing of the heads of the pillars.

Table 2. periods obtained through the simulation for the different worsening damage conditions of the building compared to that of the undamaged D0, for the first mode. Damage degree: $D1 > D2 > D3$

Period	D0 (No damage)	D1	D2	D3
T (s)	0.570	0.611	0.622	0.721

4. The results from the radar survey

To evaluate the variation actually occurred of the vibrating periods of the main modes of the building, a radar acquisition has been carried out some months later than the seismic event. The radar survey can give an estimate response of the damaged building performance.

Figure 5. Left: Scheme of the radar survey. Right: picture of the sensor: the orange ellipse indicates approximately the area corresponding to the antenna field of view.

Table 3. Radar parameters

Parameter	
Operating frequency	17.2 GHz (Ku band)
Maximum Sampling frequency	200 Hz
Maximum operating distance	1000m
Range resolution	0.5 m
Battery Autonomy	5 hours
Nominal precision	0.00001 m

The radar system used in this study works at 17.2 GHz centre frequency (Ku band), i.e. 1.743 cm wavelength in vacuum, and it allows detecting equivalent sub-millimetre displacements [8]. It is of main concern to recall that the interferometric technique can estimate distance variations only along the line of sight (LOS) direction. The phase is linearly related to the variation of the distance between the sensor and the target. Interferometric capability: the IBIS-S, manufactured and marketed by IDS (Ingegneria

dei Sistemi SpA). The system is designed for monitoring large structures and it has been largely tested by several research teams. The main operational characteristics of the system are summarized in Table 3. The system consists of a sensor module, a control PC and a power supply unit. The maximum acquisition rate is 200 Hz, but the available sampling frequency. The sensor unit is managed by control PC through a standard USB communication, which is provided with system management software, used to configure the acquisition parameters, store the measurement data and show the displacements in real time. A tripod equipped with a rotating head, used to adjust the bearing of the sensor towards the investigated structure, hold up the radar sensor. The radar is able to detect displacement components directed along the LOS and contained into the plane perpendicular to x direction (see fig.5) within the Field of view (FOV) of the antenna. Despite the difficulties of the measurements, due to the very low signal, whose peak-to-peak amplitude is of the order of a few tens of microns, the radar data allowed estimating the main vibrating frequencies. In this preliminary analysis we show the results only from bin35, the only where a good accuracy is expected using the estimated Signal to Noise Ratio [9], and where significant peaks of frequency outstand from its spectrum analysis, in the portion of the expected periods for building with similar characteristics. In fig. 6 the Power spectral density of bin35 is shown. Two main peaks are detected: 1.36 Hz ($T=0.733$) and 1.513 Hz ($T=0.661$ s). The corresponding periods are resumed in table 3. The periods measured in the experimental campaign are higher than those calculated from the numerical undamaged model indicating the presence of damage in the existing building. The ratio between the first period obtained in the experimental campaign and the corresponding first period in the modal analysis of the numerical undamaged model is about 1.28.

Table 4. Periods obtained through the radar measurements.

T (s)	0.731	0.661	0.42
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Figure 6. Power Spectral Density (PSD) calculated with the Welch method [10] applied to displacement samples obtained for bin 35. Sample duration=2160s, Overlapping 60%, Subsample=500 s.

5. Conclusions

Combining numeric modelling and experimental data acquired through an interferometric radar, the effect of an earthquake on the conditions of a building has been analysed. On the basis of the rationale that in a damaged structure the modification of the vibrating behaviour of the structure can be an indicator of a change of its stiffness, its main natural periods are expected to increase correspondingly. Numeric procedures and computational assessments allowed to evaluate the frequency expected from an undamaged building, and for the same structure when affected by different degrees of damage. The results of the radar survey are consistent with model results. This agreement allows considering radar interferometry a complementary non-invasive prospecting tool to assess the structural health conditions in a post-earthquake scenario, thus contributing to estimate the damage index, and validating the simulation results. This approach could be also used for rapid screening, immediately after the disaster with alerting and supporting purposes.

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